

“Non-seeing” Syndrome and Narration: Historicity of *Half a Life* and *Magic Seeds* in V.S.Naipaul”

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Abstract

Willie Chandran in *Half a Life* when exposed to a bigger world in England becomes aware of a very narrow world that he had been living which has eclipsed him from the rest. Then he says this “non-seeing” nature has come to him from his father. Again, he finds how ignorant he is about the greater world affairs that have never come to his notice and for this he says this “blankness” about the knowledge of the larger world has come to him from his mother. And even though he is away from his parents for more than eighteen years abroad (England and Africa) the “non-seeing” syndrome continues in him. The same nature gets reflected in the *Magic Seeds*, the sequel to *Half a Life* and remains as such until the fiction culminates. The legacy that Willie carries seems to speak much of a larger social issue that Naipaul is concerned with. The narrative of “non-seeing” and “blankness” in Willie can be read as a larger social syndrome that India carries in general and can be traced back to hundreds of years for its cognizance where it can be seen that it has been strategically designed under a colonial/racial offence:

Key terms: strategy, colonial, offence, syndrome

Willie Chandran in *Half a Life* when exposed to a bigger world in England becomes aware of a very narrow world that he had been living which has eclipsed him from the rest. Then he says this “non-seeing” nature has come to him from his father. Again, he finds how ignorant he is about the greater world affairs that have never come to his notice and for this he says this “blankness” about the knowledge of the larger world has come to him from his mother. And even though he is away from his parents for more than eighteen years abroad (England and Africa) the “non-seeing” syndrome continues in him. The same nature gets reflected in the *Magic Seeds*, the sequel to *Half a Life* and remains as such until the fiction culminates. The legacy that that Willie carries seems to speak much of a larger social issue that Naipaul is concerned with. The narrative of “non-seeing” and “blankness” in Willie can be read as a larger social syndrome that India carries in general and can be traced back to hundreds of years for its cognizance where it can be seen that it has been strategically designed under a colonial/racial offence. The aim of this paper is to retrograde through the fictions in reference to the Mughal and colonial history of India to trace the beginning of the syndrome and explore how the fictions dramatize them. In this narrative of the historicity of the texts and the textuality of the Indian history, I contend to say that Naipaul attempts to give reasons for many of the cotemporary social, historical, cultural and psychological issues that we are facing today.

Naipaul has been charged of being non-sentimental to the damage done by colonization and invasion to the former colonies. Edward Said, for instance, in his book *Reflections on Exile and Other Essays* (2000) indicts Naipaul for not being what he should have been. He goes up to the extent of labeling Naipaul as “scavenger” and charges him that, like a scavenger, he does not sympathize the postcolonial history with care and “tenderness;” does not indict imperialism for

the “derelictions” in the history: “To say that Naipaul resembles a scavenger, then, is that he now prefers to render the ruins and derelictions of postcolonial history without tenderness, without any of the sympathetic insight he prefers to indict guerillas for their pretensions rather than indict the imperialism and social injustice that drove them to insurrection...(100). However, at least in the fiction in reference and India as their context, Naipaul’s stand does not get fit in Said. I will argue that the post-independent history in general and Marxist guerilla movement in particular in the south India which are marked by the sense of the syndrome have found the post-colonial interpretation in Naipaul. Therefore, as far as Naipaul is concerned the indictment of Said appears only a hasty generalization.

In the first book *An Area of Darkness* (1964) on his Indian trilogy his first impression of India is a shock. It has remained a mysterious place for him existing only in his imagination with information collected from the tales at his domestic discourse in Trinidad. On his first visit the imagination collapses when it is exposed to reality leaving behind only shock and horror. He thus writes about India: “ It still horrifies me that people should put out food for animals on plates that they themselves use...at school to see boys sharing Popsicles and Palates...to see women sipping from ladies with which they stir their pots...this was the uncleanliness we had to guard against...” (35). What worries Naipaul more is that the “uncleanliness” was not seen in India as the Indians have been habituated to non-seeing and is being handed down to generation. In *Half a Life*, when Willie becomes aware of the presence of a larger world in England that he has not seen yet he gives it a legacy twist and says “This habit of non-seeing I have got from my father” (54). At other time when he realizes that he is too closed to the larger world and “swimming in ignorance” yet, he makes his mother responsible. In other words, Willie is confirming that non-seeing and ignorance are there in the genes of Indians:

Willie thought he was swimming in ignorance, had lived without a knowledge of time. He remembered one of the things his mother’s uncle used to say: that the backwards had been shut out for so long from society that they knew nothing of India, nothing of the other religions,

nothing even of the religion of the people of caste, whose serfs they were. And he thought, 'This blankness is one of the things I have got from my mother's side (55).

However, the shock and horror evaporates in the second book *India: A Wounded Civilization* (1977) as he comes in terms with the reality. In the second book he thus confesses that it has taken him much time to think about and come to terms with the "strangeness of India." On his visit to the debris of the ancient Vijayanagara kingdom in the south, which marked the ancient Indian epitome of perfection in art and intellect, he starts giving the not seeing habit of Indians a historical bent which bears the stamps of a colonial offence. Standing on the site, he thus imagines "I began to wonder about the intellectual depletion that must have come to India with the invasions and the conquests of the last thousand years. What happened in Vijayanagara happened, in varying degrees, in other parts of the country" (07). The direct reference is to the Mughal invasion of India followed by the British and their psychological offence on the Indians. In those last thousand years Indians have forgotten what they were and remembered only what they were strategically made to believe that they are only the unclean "servile" class. This has slowly become an eternal truth for them. This wondering of Naipaul goes into the beginning of the fabric of his fiction *Magic Seeds* so as to indicate the fiction is a meditation on the socio-historical dimension of India. The beauty of the meditation is that it historicizes the text and textualizes the history and within the equation emerges the face of contemporary India that demands introspection at several levels.

The title of the second fiction *Magic Seeds* directly connects the history of India to the colonial. It is taken from an English fairytale *Jack and the Beanstalk* in which a boy named Jack climbs through the beanstalk of some magical beans and reaches at the rich palace of a giant in the sky. He steals all the riches from the giant and brings them back to his place on the earth. On his last trip to the earth, the giant pursues him to fight back the riches but no sooner on the earth he cuts the beanstalk through which he has climbed out and kills the giant following him through the same. In other words, it is the story of theft. Naipaul gives the story a colonial bent. Jack is the allegorical figure of the colonizer and the giant the colonial "other." The killing of the giant becomes parallel to the devastation brought by the colonization.

In the fiction the story encompasses both Mughal empire and the British colonization in India. The killing of the giant gets figured in the “intellectual” depletion of Indians as a ramification of their strategy of servility both the conquerors adopt and promote.

In *Magic Seeds* Willie in the very beginning of the fiction returns to India to join a Marxist guerilla movement in south India which is supposed to have been meant for the emancipation of the servile class. While towards the place of his recruitment, he is received by a sympathizer of the movement, a teacher named Joseph who takes him to the debris of the Vijayanagara Kingdom and gradually unfolds its history while trying to co-relate the movement with the consequence of the fall of the kingdom. He thus narrates,

We are on the site of the last great Indian kingdom, and it was the site of a catastrophe. Four hundred years ago the Muslim invaders ganged up on it and destroyed it. They spent weeks, possibly months, destroying it. They leveled the capital city. It was a rich and famous city known to early European travelers. They killed the priests, the philosophers, the artisans, the architects, the scholars. They knew what they were doing. They were cutting of the head. The only people they left behind were the serfs in the villages, and they parceled them among themselves. This military defeat was terrible (37).

Joseph confirms that only the serfs were left and transported throughout India as the servile class to the Mughal rulers. There was no resistance from them, rather they cannot do that. Their work is to run before and after the horses of their masters, they do grave digging and scavenging and some of them even offer their women to their lords. They gradually refer to themselves as “slaves.” And Joseph adds “After four hundred years of this kind of rule the people here would have grown to believe that this was their eternal condition (38).

However, with the coming of British the Mughal dynasty ends but the pattern of the servility remained as it was though its form goes transmutation. Sarojini, the sister of Willie, claims that “since in India we have no idea of history we quickly forget our past and always believe what we are told” (07). But not having the idea of the history is also a part of the colonial strategy as pointed above by Joseph.

Upon that the history Indians read is Eurocentric. While educating Willie on India, Sarojini refers to Roper Lethbridge history they read in their schools written by a nineteenth-century English inspector of school. The book proposes a wrong idea of the servile class, a development upon the servile class created and promoted by the Mughals. She says the Lethbridge history gave many ideas that Indian carries of which the idea of the servile class is one of them:

One of the most important of those ideas was that in India there were servile races, people born to be slaves, and there were martial races...And that British idea about the servile and martial races of India is utterly wrong. The British East India Company arms in the north of India was a Hindu army of the upper castes...But after the great Mutiny of 1857 ...Further military opportunities were denied them. So the warriors who had won the empire became servile in British propaganda and the frontier people they had conquered just before the mutiny became the martial ones (7).

What Sarojini claims is that the “servile” class is also a British creation; those who do not fit into their system and are risky were gradually transformed into the servile. Both during the Mughal and British imperialism of around eight hundred years, according to Naipaul, the Indians were strategically denied the idea of their history, they suffer intellectual depletion, and what is taught to them becomes a part of their eternal belief. They become “non-seeing” and accordingly their understanding of themselves and the world around to a large extent is eclipsed by a claustrophobic “blankness.” They simply become uncritical, just the career of others ideals. This becomes a legacy of the generation which gets manifested in terms of Willie’s father, himself in both the fictions and guerillas in the second which I will explore next.

What Naipaul says in *India: A Wounded Civilization* about the probable intellectual depletion following the destruction from the Mughal invasion and the British and Joseph in *Magic Seeds* about the destruction of the Vijayanagara Kingdom also is the history of the great-great grandfather of Willie. As a consequence of the invasion and the colonization, towards 1890s, the village of his grandfather was devastated. People of his community were reduced to pauper who were at one point of time were very

rich and prosperous Brahmin community. The invasion and its narration by the father of Willie bring much of the history into the fabric of the fiction *Half a Life*:

At one time I suppose we would have been a very rich and prosperous community. But when the Muslims conquered the land we all became poor. The people we served could no longer support us. Things became worse when the British came...All the complicated rules of the community held, but there was actually very little to eat. People became thin and weak and fell ill easily (5).

The burden of invasion made the great-great grandfather leave his village, like many others, in search of life and accordingly he made his way for the town. For the survival of the family he is forced to go to the maharaja of a town and ended in one of his temple yards and eventually into the palace where he was confined for the rest of his life, the world beyond becomes unseeing and blank. And this has an effect of shortsightedness in the generation, the father of Willie being the most affected.

Naipaul has been charged of being too close to Hindu ideology and way of life by some critics for his dealing with Hindu way of life of people like the father of Willie. According to Professor Mohamed Bakari , a Turkish critic, “As a Brahmin he feels duty bound to be in the forefront...to defend Indian culture and Hinduism...” (248). However, Bakari seems to be too subjective in his statement because the stand of Naipaul on Brahminism has always remained very critical; there are deviations from and assaults on it. Willie’s father thinks of deviation from his ancestry of Brahminic origin. He says he “My decision was simple. It was to turn my back on our ancestry...” (10) meaning that he will simply not practice the family convention. But he does not see what he is doing. The “non-seeing” syndrome compounds in him under the Gandhian spell of 1930s when he decides to give up his university education and joins the movement. He gives up his struggle to education and surrenders to mahatma. Critics have noted this surrender in Naipaul as surrender to Indian fatalism. As such Bruce Kings comments that Naipaul “... has also been attracted to giving up the struggle, accepting nothingness, withdrawing into inactivity, Indian fatalism” (King 22). But in case of the father of Willie, his act is a stupidity and not fatalism. He foolishly gives up and fails his university education. He

thinks he wants to live a life of sacrifice, like the mahatma, and accordingly starts looking companion in a Dalit girl in the university canteen. He makes a “bonfire” of the books in front of the university and the rest of the time starts running after the girl. His companion with the girl spreads like a wild fire and he is forced to hide her fearing a backlash from her family. Occasionally he visits her to provide for and in the meantime, to his shock, the girl becomes pregnant. When he sees and realizes what he is doing, it is already too late to redeem. He thus says, “I took a vow of sexual abstinence, a vow of *brahmacharya*. Like the Mahatma. Unlike him, I failed. I was full of shame. And I was very swiftly punished. I soon afterwards had to recognize that the girl was pregnant... (33) and when she becomes pregnant for the second time, he regrets, “It was like divine punishment” (35).

Willie feels the burden of the syndrome. His first reaction to his father having heard of his story is contempt. He says, “I despise you” (35) and concludes “What is there for me in what you have said? You offer me nothing”(35). The reaction of Willie seems Oedipal but the immediate cause is his father’s incapacity to see through the things and its ramification in him. This impacts their relation throughout the rest of their life. Willie remains always ironical to his father; he condemns his life of sacrifice that has turned to himself. In the meantime, he too gives up his mission school and the father is least bothered about the giving up. Eventually, he goes to London in a scholarship to join a teacher-training college. But he always has allergy for the education. Later on in *Magic Seeds* the narrator informs us that Willie “had been frustrated by his mission school and the London teacher-training college” (229). Willie gives up the school that may be a childish impulse, but his frustration in the college is nothing but a legacy, it is the part of his own father. Education does not matter him much, this is his non-seeing. It was just the time of the beginning of new education system in India and he could have groomed his future with a good job back home had he had successfully completed his training. But he does not see this. Deviated from the purpose and a promising future, he ends in the plebian life of London, goes with prostitutes and eventually is all at lost. Until his scholarship comes, he achieves nothing. At last frustrated and scared

proposes an African girl, Anna, so as to anchor him from the impending chaos. This decision is impulsive and yet another instance of non-seeing in him who, like his father, regrets at the end.

In Africa, he stays for eighteen years but does not achieve or do anything concrete. He is a refugee at Anna. She is his safety. He says “I believed that she was in some essential way guided and protected, and as long as I was with her no harm could come to me” (141). But soon he starts betraying her visiting prostitutes in bars. He does not see the generosity of Anna, nor does what he is doing, nor feels remorse for that. Only when he is exhausted with the prostitutes, he goes to Anna. He says, “It was in this enervated mood that I began to make love to Ana again, hoping to recover the closeness that had once seemed so natural” (195). He justifies his going to prostitutes referring to the restriction to open sex that his father had in the ashram. When Anna becomes concerned and terms his act as “madness” to be with the prostitutes, he reciprocates; no longer feels that he belongs to her:

I let it (the reaction of Ana) pass. I had no wish to quarrel with her...old love and regard for her had welled up in me. Old love: it was still there, it could even be added to at moments like this, but it belonged now to another life, or a part of my life that had run its course. I no longer slept in her grandfather's big carved bed... (216).

Eventually, a guerilla war breaks out and people start fleeing. The war is purely racial in nature. Then there are counter guerillas who challenge the former. The former is supported by the native Africans and the later by the Western governments and thus the place is virtually divided. Willie realizes the gravity of the situation, suddenly feels unsecured and decides to withdraw from Africa. As usual, he does not see wars come and go and there will be a resolution sooner or later. Only after eighteen years, when it is too late, when he is almost fourteen years he sees that he is not living his life. Thu he says to Anna, “I've given you eighteen years. I can't give you any more. I can't live your life any more. I want to live my own” (136). And the paradox of the

situation is that Willie does not see how to start the life of his own. It is her sister, Sarojini, who seems to be better than him sums up in *Magic Seeds* what Willie actually is, how he is a legacy of the colonial psychosis. She indicts him, “You’ve never felt there was anything for you to do. You’ve never understood that men have to make the world for themselves. You’ve always preferred to hide. It’s the colonial psychosis, the caste psychosis. You inherited it from your father (1-2).

Thus Willie is always non-seeing which he inherits from his father. He confesses “...all the old ghosts were already with me, the ghosts of home...” (187) meaning the blood that he has inherited from the non-sophisticated father and servile class mother. And yet, Naipaul has used the same non-seeing and blank protagonist as an insider to study the guerilla movement in *Magic Seeds* in the south India. The politics behind using a non-seeing and non-critical man to study the guerillas seems that a seeing and thinking individual will certainly not join. Naipaul needs just an informer and Willie can do that well without being critical. When one does not have or loses critical faculty, chances for gullibility is maximum. This is exactly the situation of Willie in the hand of Sarojini. Willie has returned, lost, to Sarojini in Berlin. For her, Willie is a failure. She draws from Gandhi who was also a failure like him in the beginning in London and South Africa. “I know now that you were no different from Mahatma Gandhi...” (16), she says to Willie. Further she asks, “Don’t you feel you can see yourself a little bit in that young Gandhi?” (17). Gandhi, though a failure in the beginning, could lead the people the greater cause using thought and intuition. Sarojini carries away Willie; she persuades him to join the Marxist guerrilla movement in south India which is supposed to be meant for the emancipation of the exploitation of the servile class led by a man called Kandapalli Seetaramiah. Willie feels that he can become

another Gandhi and until now he is being prepared for that. He assumes that "...everything that had happened to him was a preparation for what was now to come" (23).

Willie is non-seeing and so are the cadres that he comes across in the movement. For many of them their reason for joining the movement has nothing to do with the emancipation of the servile class. Their reasons are strange. They have no idea of their enemy, neither have they known why and for whom are they fighting. People join the naxalites because of the non-seeing syndrome only. Joseph, for instance, who receives Willie when he arrives in India from Berlin keeps a "slave" girl to work for him from the servile class. He calls himself "cheerleader" for the guerillas. A slave girl in his place whose emancipation is the supposed mission of the organization is a refusal to see the organizational goal. One of the leaders, Willie reports, looks more like a "businessman" than a naxalite leader. Bhoj Narayan, a cadre, joined the movement because he had heard in a story that a peasant was killed by his master in old days which boiled his blood for vengeance. But the irony is that he does not know who that master was and whom to revenge. Likewise Einstein has another story. Out of his stupidity he had lost his university job. He thought of correcting Albert Einstein and gradually became a maniac and the university authority had to fire him. As a part of the revenge he joined the movement. Another man Raja joined just to escape from village boredom. The reason of Ramachandra, the unit commander, is equally queer. During his college days, he proposed a girl. She did not budge because he was a failure in studies. He was driven by youth sexual urge and even if he wooed girls for satisfaction, he could draw none towards him. So as a part of the vengeance, he joined the movement.

What is terribly missing in the purpose of joining the movement is their inability to see the mission of the organization. Willie realizes this and manages to surrender to the police and eventually gets amnesty and returns to London for the rest of his life. When the novel closes, we

find a seemingly awakened Willie who seems to have realized the inherent line of fallacy in him. His legacy is always driven by the ideas of others: his father was driven by the idea of mahatma which landed him in a disaster; his going to London to be trained as a teacher was the idea of his father which catapulted him to the plebeian English culture and thereafter to the chaos of Africa and the idea of Sarojini pushed him to the naxalite where he eventually landed in jail. His gullibility to the others' ideas and his inability, the non-seeing syndrome, to access them critically always problematized him and eventually ruined his active period of life. At the end he realizes the line of the fallacy in him and comes to the conclusion that "It is wrong to have an ideal view of the world. That's where the mischief starts. That's where everything starts unraveling" (293) .

Willie's realization is equally true of the guerillas. They had never seen the goal of the organization and it continues thus. About the mutinies , Naipaul comments in the third book *India: A Million Mutinies Now* (1990) that Indian people have of late realized the offence on their servility and accordingly there were several mutinies for emancipation and the mutinies "were part of India's growth, part of its restoration" (1077). But the *Magic Seeds* published after fourteen years does not endorse the idea. The mutinies might be the form of the "restoration" and yet they are not free from the syndrome. The strategic idea designed by the invasion and the empire is psychologically mimicked in India. Bhabha has traced a line of descent of the mimicry that Naipaul exhibits in many other writers too. He says "The line of descent of the mimic man can be traced through the works of Kipling, Forster, Orwell, and Naipaul..." (Bhabha 87). He seems to suggest that Naipaul carries the idea manufactured and promoted by the nineteenth century European writers. However, in Naipaul there is also an eraser to this embodiment. His characters in the fiction in reference do not simply mimic the empirical values designed by the

foreign empires; rather the texts historicize the injuries and damage caused to their civilization in terms of the syndrome and their psychological ramification in them.

A solution to the syndrome that Naipaul prescribes may be to discard the ideal view of the world as Willie concludes the fiction and get down to the reality to become practical. But the pragmatic side is yet to be tested in Naipaul, that is to say how far his suggestion works, as the fiction ends there and we do not see what Willie does next. Neither have we found another work on India by Naipaul after *Magic Seeds* so as to witness a practical hero unlike Willie. And yet what is achieved in Naipaul is that history gets textualized and the fictions get historicized. This achieved history in the fictions and the achieved fiction in the history, the point of intersection between them, really dramatizes a deeper social and cerebral damage caused to a great civilization manifested by the Vijayanagara Kingdom by the foreign invasions and the colonization. This really conditions us to start re-thinking about the linear history and its inadequacy to reflect on micro social, historical, cultural and psychological syndrome that India is battling with. In this sense the historicity of the Naipaulean fictions is aimed at becoming cause and condition for a new intellectual awakening in India.

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